

Kinetics of Sucrose Inversion by Adiabatic Temperature Measurements.

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Variation in the heat content of a reactive system is amongst the most conspicuous results produced by a chemical change. It is to be anticipated, therefore, that a parallelism would exist between the progress of a reaction and of the corresponding time variation of the temperature of the system. In a study on this basis of the kinetics of a change, an adequate thermal insulation of the reactive system, and a reckoning of the possible influence of the temperature on the rate of change would appear to be the chief factors requiring a careful consideration. Bredig and Epstein (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1904, **42**, 341) appear to have been perhaps the first to recognise the general utility of this method, and Barry (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, **42**, 1911, 1926) to use it in the kinetics of sucrose inversion. It was felt, however, that need existed for a modified procedure yielding data both accurate and in a form which can be treated directly from a theoretical standpoint. Measurements have been also carried out on the specific heat of sucrose solution and the influence of sucrose on the heat of dilution of hydrochloric acid by water.

In his work Barry (*loc. cit.*) introduced a known amount of solid sucrose in the acid of the desired strength kept in the calorimeter. The dissolution of sucrose in an acid solution is endothermic. This effect is partly superimposed upon that due to sucrose inversion. The temperature of the reaction mixture would, therefore, rise slower in the *initial* stages. It was also felt that this would add to the initial period of disturbance which obtains when even liquids are mixed, and which has been ascribed to the slow homogenisation of the reaction mixture (*cf.* especially Scatchard, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **48**, 2259 ; also, Lambie and Lewis, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, **105**, 2330). In the following experiments a definite amount of the acid solution has been added to a sucrose solution in the calorimeter. Furthermore, unlike Barry, the temperature measurements have been restricted only to the *initial* stages of the inversion so that the temperature rise is not appreciable ; this is necessary since the reaction is known to be sensitive to temperature changes (*vide infra*).

EXPERIMENTAL.

The reaction was carried out in a Dewar flask of about 600 c.c. capacity and was enclosed in a heavy copper cylinder leaving an air

gap of 1 cm. The cylinder and the Dewar flask were fitted respectively with a copper and an ebonite cap, each of which was perforated to admit a Beckmann thermometer, the stem of a small funnel and a perforated, reciprocating gold stirrer, operating vertically. The copper cylinder was placed in a water thermostat of about 90 litres capacity, whose temperature was kept constant at 30° within 0.01° . The Dewar flask contained 250 c.c. of sucrose solution of the desired concentration and was heated electrically to 30° in all the experiments. 50 C c. of a solution of hydrochloric acid of known strength preheated to 30° were then added carefully through the funnel to the sucrose solution, and the corresponding time noted. The weight of this solution of the hydrochloric acid added varied in the range, 51.48 to 51.6 g. in the various experiments. The temperature of the mixture was then observed within 0.001° at regular intervals by means of a Beckmann thermometer and a special telescope. Figs. 1-4 show the Beckmann readings with time during sucrose inversions by four acid concentrations. The strength of the sucrose solution is expressed in terms of the weight in g. of the solute in 100 c.c. of the reaction mixture at 30° and the stirring of the mixture, which was started before the addition of the acid, was so regulated that there was no sensible thermal lag in the record of the temperature by the Beckmann thermometer (except curve 4, Fig. 4). Curve 6 in Fig. 6 is a typical curve showing the Beckmann reading during the progress of one inversion. AB, the horizontal part of this curve denotes time of constant temperature before this addition of the acid. The sudden rise in BC is due to the dilution of the acid added (*vide infra*). Progress of the inversion is, therefore, represented only by the last section of the curve, CD. In order to economise space and prevent overlapping, these temperature-time readings have been presented graphically in Figs. 1-4, after the addition of a convenient constant to the series of Beckmann readings obtained for any given inversion. In drawing these curves points corresponding to sections AB and BC in curve 6 of Fig. 6 have not been employed. For example, the actual Beckmann readings at different times during inversion of 15 % sucrose solution by 4.92N-HCl are shown graphically by curve 6 in Fig. 6. Curve 4 in Fig. 3 was drawn from this by subtracting 2.125 from the Beckmann readings plotted in the section CD (curve 6, Fig. 6). It is obvious that this procedure does not alter the *time rate* of temperature rise in a given inversion. On the other hand it has the advantage of representing the time-temperature curves characteristic of the inversions of variously

concentrated sucrose solutions in the same figure and with the same co-ordinates. These curves shown in Figs. 1-4 refer to inversions in which the acid strength was varied in the range 0.4 to 0.9N, and that of the sugar from about 2 to 30 % by weight of the reaction mixture. From these curves as explained later, the values of k , the velocity coefficients for sugar inversion at various sugar and acid concentrations have been deduced and the results shown in Tables I-IV.

It will be seen from the typical time-temperature curve 6 of Fig. 6 that there is at first a large and a sudden rise of temperature which is followed by a slower rise. The first temperature rise is due almost entirely to the heat of dilution of the acid and is followed by that due to inversion. The two sections are separated by an appreciable discontinuity in the curve. Moreover, the second section begins fairly close to the temperature axis. The temperature rise due to the first factor, *viz.*, acid dilution is obtained easily by the extrapolation of the curve for zero time. Curves 1-4 of Fig. 6 show the variation of this initial temperature rise for the variously concentrated sugar solutions when mixed with acid solutions of different strengths as mentioned already. Curve 5 in Fig. 6 shows the rise of temperature produced in equal amounts of sugar solutions in the same range of dilution as above when heated by exactly the same quantity of electrical energy (*cf.* 7th column, Table V).

It was also thought desirable to measure the specific heats of sugar solutions at different dilutions (*cf.* Table V) and it was done by the electrical method. 1.1610 amp. was allowed to flow 9 minutes through about 300 c.c. of the solution. The consequent temperature rise was about 3°. The radiation correction varied in the range 0.03 to 0.046°. The accuracy of these measurements is shown by the fact that the water equivalent of the calorimeter could be reproduced within 0.6 %. Details regarding the technique of these measurements will be described in a later communication. Curve 5 in Fig. 5 and (indirectly curve 5 in Fig. 6) relate respectively the specific heat of solutions of sucrose and of invert sugar with the acid concentration. Curves 1-4 in Fig. 5 show the values of k , the velocity coefficient calculated for the initial stages of the inversion (*vide infra*), (*cf.* Tables I-IV) for four series of sugar concentrations, the acid strengths being kept constant in a given series. ' m ' in Tables I-IV denotes the strength of the sucrose solution in g. of the solute per 100 c.c. of the reaction mixture at 30°; ' t ' and ' T ' denote interval in minutes and temperature respectively; ' k ' denotes velocity coefficient for sugar inversion.

TABLE I.
HCl conc. = 0.807N.

t.	m.	→	2	3	4	5	6	8	10	13
1 min.	$\frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t}$		0.0025/1	0.00325/1	0.0065/1	0.0080/1	0.0110/1	0.0150/1	0.0180/1	0.0425/1
	" k		0.0025 0.00125	0.00325 0.001083	0.0065 0.001625	0.0080 0.001600	0.0110 0.00183	0.0150 0.00187	0.0180 0.00180	0.0425 0.00327
2.5	$\frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t}$		0.0065/2.5	0.0100/2.5	0.0160/2.5	0.0185/2.5	0.0265/2.5	0.0345/2.5	0.0460/2.5	0.1050/2.5
	" k		0.0026 0.0013	0.0040 0.00133	0.0064 0.0016	0.0074 0.00148	0.0106 0.00176	0.0138 0.001725	0.0184 0.00184	0.0420 0.00323
5.0	$\frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t}$		0.0120/5	0.0200/5	0.0320/5	0.0375/5	0.0520/5	0.0690/5	0.09055	0.2150/5
	" k		0.0024 0.00120	0.0040 0.001330	0.0064 0.001600	0.0075 0.001500	0.01040 0.00173	0.0138 0.00172	0.0181 0.00181	0.0430 0.00330
10	$\frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t}$		0.024/10	0.0405/10	0.0610/10	0.0730/10	0.0940/10	0.1365/10	0.1765/10	
	" k		0.0024 0.00120	0.00405 0.00135	0.00610 0.001525	0.00730 0.00146	0.00940 0.00156	0.01365 0.00170	0.01765 0.001765	
15	$\frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t}$		0.0350/15	0.0560/15	0.0840/15	0.1050/15	0.1340/15	0.1890/15	0.249/15	
	" k		0.00233 0.001166	0.00373 0.00124	0.0056 0.0014	0.0070 0.0014	0.00893 0.001486	0.0126 0.00157	0.0166 0.00166	
20	$\frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t}$		0.0450/20	0.0690/20	0.1050/20	0.1310/20	0.1720/20	0.2390/20	0.3160/20	
	" k		0.00225 0.001125	0.00345 0.00115	0.00525 0.00131	0.00655 0.00131	0.0086 0.00143	0.01195 0.001493	0.0158 0.00158	

TABLE II.

HCl conc. = 0.83N.

t	$m.$	\rightarrow	1	2	4	6	8	10	13
1 min.	$\frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t}$		0.0005/1	0.0020/1	0.0060/1	0.0110/1	0.0180/1	0.0220/1	0.0290/1
"	" k		0.0005	0.0020	0.0060	0.0110	0.0180	0.0220	0.0290
"	"		0.0005	0.0010	0.0015	0.00171	0.00225	0.0022	0.00223
2.5	$\frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t}$		0.00015/2.5		0.016/2.5	0.028/2.5	0.043/2.5	0.053/2.5	0.076/2.5
"	" k		0.0006		0.0064	0.0112	0.0172	0.0212	0.0304
"	"		0.0006		0.0016	0.00186	0.00215	0.00212	0.002338
5	$\frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t}$		0.003/5	0.004/5	0.0310/5	0.0510/5	0.0880/5	0.1040/5	0.1420/5
"	" k		0.0006	0.0008	0.0062	0.0102	0.0176	0.0208	0.0284
"	"		0.0006	0.0004	0.00155	0.00170	0.00220	0.00208	0.00219
10	$\frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t}$		0.005/10		0.0610/10	0.105/10	0.1530/10	0.1850/10	0.2700/10
"	" k		0.0005		0.00610	0.0105	0.0153	0.0185	0.0270
"	"		0.0005		0.001525	0.00176	0.00191	0.00185	0.00207
15	$\frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t}$		0.008/15		0.086/15	0.147/15	0.215/15	0.260/15	0.280/15
"	" k		0.00053		0.00578	0.00980	0.0143	0.0173	0.0186
"	"		0.00053		0.00143	0.00163	0.00179	0.00173	0.001435
20	$\frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t}$					0.185/20	0.271/20	0.324/20	
"	" k					0.00925	0.01355	0.0162	
"	"					0.001541	0.001693	0.00162	

TABLE III.

HCl conc. = 0.82N.

<i>t.</i>	<i>m.</i> →	5	10	15	20	25	30
1 min.	$\frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t}$	0.0075/1	0.015/1	0.028/1	0.040/1	0.035/1	0.052/1
„	„	0.075	0.015	0.028	0.040	0.035	0.052
„	<i>k</i>	0.0015	0.0015	0.00186	0.00200	0.0014	0.00173
2.5	$\frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t}$	0.018/2.5	0.035/2.5	0.070/2.5	0.099/2.5	0.091/2.5	0.1275/2.5
„	„	0.0072	0.014	0.028	0.0396	0.0364	0.0510
„	<i>k</i>	0.00145	0.0014	0.00186	0.00198	0.001456	0.0017
5	$\frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t}$	0.035/5	0.070/5	0.140/5	0.195/5	0.180/5	0.260/5
„	„	0.007	0.0014	0.028	0.039	0.036	0.052
„	<i>k</i>	0.0014	0.0014	0.00186	0.00195	0.00144	0.00173
10	$\frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t}$	0.067/10		0.265/10	0.390/10	0.358/10	0.517/10
„	„	0.0067		0.0265	0.039	0.0358	0.0517
„	<i>k</i>	0.00134		0.00176	0.00195	0.00143	0.00172
15	$\frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t}$	0.096/15	0.193/15	0.380/15	0.556/15	0.535/15	0.752/15
„	„	0.0064	0.01286	0.0253	0.03706	0.0356	0.05013
„	<i>k</i>	0.00128	0.001286	0.001686	0.001853	0.001424	0.001671
20	$\frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t}$	0.125/20	0.242/20	0.483/20	0.706/20	0.695/20	0.954/20
„	„	0.00625	0.0121	0.02415	0.0353	0.03475	0.0477
„	<i>k</i>	0.00125	0.00121	0.00161	0.001765	0.00139	0.00159

TABLE IV.

HCl=0.41N.

<i>t.</i>	<i>m.</i> →	5	10	15	20	25	30
1 min	$\frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t}$	0.004/1	0.006/1	0.009/1	0.013/1	0.020/1	0.0215/1
"	"	0.004	0.006	0.009	0.013	0.020	0.0215
"	<i>k</i>	0.00080	0.00060	0.00060	0.00065	0.00080	0.00071
2.5	$\frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t}$	0.0095/2.5	0.0125/2.5	0.021/2.5	0.033/2.5	0.0495/2.5	0.0515/2.5
"	"	0.0038	0.0050	0.0084	0.0132	0.0198	0.0206
"	<i>k</i>	0.00076	0.00050	0.00056	0.00066	0.000792	0.000686
5	$\frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t}$	0.019/5	0.026/5	0.043/5	0.066/5	0.100/5	0.102/5
"	"	0.0038	0.0052	0.0086	0.0132	0.020	0.0204
"	<i>k</i>	0.00076	0.00052	0.00057	0.00066	0.00080	0.00068
10	$\frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t}$	0.0375/10	0.050/10	0.0845/10	0.133/10	0.198/10	0.2005/10
"	"	0.00375	0.0050	0.00845	0.0133	0.0198	0.02005
"	<i>k</i>	0.00075	0.00050	0.00056	0.00066	0.00079	0.00066
15	$\frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t}$	0.0545/15	0.0750/15	0.124/15	0.195/15	0.2915/15	0.299/15
"	"	0.00363	0.005	0.00826	0.0130	0.01941	0.01993
"	<i>k</i>	0.000726	0.00050	0.0005507	0.00065	0.0007765	0.000664
20	$\frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t}$	0.070/20	0.098/20	0.163/20	0.258/20	0.379/20	0.390/20
"	"	0.0035	0.0049	0.00815	0.0129	0.01895	0.0195
"	<i>k</i>	0.00070	0.00049	0.000543	0.000645	0.000758	0.00065

TABLE V.

Vol. of the sucrose soln. 300 ± 0.05 c.c. (50°). P.D. across the heating coils = 6.8250 volts. Current passed = 1.1610 amps. during 540 sec.

Sucrose soln.	Comp. and wt. of soln.				Initial temp.	Final temp.	Temp. rise.	Sp. heat.
	Sucrose	+	Water	= Soln.				
0%	0.0g.	+	298.6g.	= 298.6g.	2.225	5.313	3.088	0.9987
2	6.0	+	294.4	= 300.4	2.120	5.215	3.095	0.9860
4	12.0	+	289.6	= 301.6	2.190	5.314	3.124	0.9716
8	24.0	+	283.5	= 307.5	2.284	5.424	3.140	0.9479
13	39.0	+	274.4	= 313.4	2.240	5.579	3.159	0.9239
Invert sugar								
10.5	31.6 g	+	272.1 g.	= 303.7g.	1.960	5.192	3.232	0.9335
				(309.9)	—	—	(3.1672)	—
21.1	63.2	+	254.0	= 317.2	2.004	5.192	3.188	0.9074
31.6	94.7	+	223.5	= 318.2	1.870	5.098	3.228	0.8921

DISCUSSION.

It is seen from the curves in Figs. 1-4 (in which the *initial* temperature rise due to the dilution of the acid is not shown),—with the exception of curve 3 in Fig 2 and curve 4 of Fig. 4, that the progress of inversion is accompanied by a continuous rise of temperature as a result of the accumulation of the heat due to the change in the reaction vessel (which is thermally insulated from the environment, *vis.*, the thermostat kept at a constant temperature). This temperature rise over the initial temperature in the reaction vessel varied in the range 0.006° to 0.42° (*cf.* curves 2 and 7 in Fig. 2 and 3 respectively). The observed time-temperature curves are, therefore, subject to but negligible correction in respect of the influence of the temperature on the rate of sucrose inversion. Furthermore, these

observations were taken during about 20-25 minutes from the commencement of the change. They represent, therefore, but the initial stages of the reaction.

It is interesting to note from the curves in Figs. 1-4 that the time-rate of the temperature rise due to sucrose inversion increases by increasing the sucrose concentration, if the acid concentration is kept constant. Similar to this is the influence of varying the acid concentration, that of sucrose being kept constant. This last is to be anticipated in view of the well known influence of the acid concentration on the inversion rate, which determines the rate of the temperature rise produced in the system during the reaction.

It is to be noted from curve 5 in Fig. 6, showing the temperature rise when a fixed quantity of heat produced electrically was dissipated in a constant weight of variously concentrated solutions of sucrose and of invert sugar, that the specific heats for the latter (*cf.* p' , q and r , in the above curve) can be represented fairly well on the specific heat-concentration curve for sucrose, *viz.*, curve 5 in Fig. 6. This together with the data recorded in Table V shows that the heat capacity of sucrose solution does not change appreciably due to inversion. Since the acid concentration remains constant during inversion and that the maximum rise in temperature produced is about 0.32° only (during about 25 minutes), it has been assumed during the subsequent discussion that C_v , the heat capacity at constant volume of the reaction mixture remains constant during inversion.

Following the usual notation and denoting by Δq , the heat evolved corresponding to Δx , the amount of sucrose inverted.

$$\frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} = k' (a - x) \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (i)$$

$$= k' \cdot \frac{\Delta q}{\Delta t} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (ii)$$

$$= k' \cdot C_v \cdot \frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (iii)$$

$$= k'' \cdot \frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (iv)$$

At initial stages when to first approximation x is negligible compared with a , we get from (i) and (iv),

$$k = \frac{1}{a} \cdot \frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (v)$$

where k is a measure of velocity constant. The values for the quantity $\Delta T/\Delta t$ have been obtained from the t - T curves in Figs. 1-4. The velocity coefficient k is then obtained simply from (v). On examining the k values in Tables I-IV it is seen that during any given inversion, k diminishes with time which is to be anticipated from the approximation introduced in neglecting x compared with a during the early stages of the change. At early stages, however, the values of the velocity coefficient are fairly concordant. This warrants, therefore, to a considerable extent the chief assumption made earlier, especially as regards C_v .

The k values used in drawing curves 1-4 in Fig. 5 have been calculated from data obtained only for the initial stages of the inversions for reasons indicated above. It is seen that except in curve 4 of Fig. 5 corresponding to the smallest acid concentration, k increases considerably with the increase of the initial sucrose concentration. In the familiar mass law expression,

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k_{v,i} [\text{water}] \times [\text{sucrose}]$$

since the inversion produces ordinarily but negligible variations in the amount of water present, it is considered to be unimolecular. The $k_{v,i} \times [\text{water}]$ is, therefore, practically constant, and equals the ordinary velocity coefficient k . Since $k_{v,i}$ is constant, and the proportion of water diminishes by increasing that of sucrose in a given mass of solution, it follows that k should diminish, which is contrary to experience. The possible variation of the active mass of water operating but *hydrolytically* according to the above equation can not, therefore, account for the observed increase of k by increasing the sucrose concentration at constant acid strength. Similar results have been obtained by numerous workers (cf. Cohen, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1897, 23, 442; Jones and Lewis, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 1120; Moron and Lewis, *ibid.*, 1922, 121, 1613; Cotton and Chandun, *compt. rend.*, 1924, 179, 1607; 1926, 182, 775; 1926, 183, 1215) and have been ascribed to an increase in the thermodynamic activity of the H ions. Change of k as observed has been also attributed by some workers to the

the reduced formation of the unstable sucrose-water complexes (which break up into dextrose and laevulose at a rate proportional to the concentration of the complexes) as a result of the diminution of the water constant (Cotton and Chandun, *loc. cit.*). That the influence of the last factor might be appreciable is indicated by the data in column 3, Table V showing the amount of water present in the various solutions of sucrose used. Whilst therefore in agreement with this, the results in Table I-III and curves 1-9 in Fig. 5 showing the increase in k by increasing the sucrose concentration are to be anticipated, it is interesting to note from our results that this increase in k appears to be a function of the acid concentration.

It has been mentioned already that immediately on mixing together the solutions of sucrose and of the acid, a rapid rise of temperature (BC, in curve 6, Fig 6) was produced due to the evolution of the dilution heat of the acid. This temperature rise varied in the range 0.86° to 0.09° (*cf.* curves 1 to 4 in Fig. 6). It is seen from these curves that the *initial* temperature rise diminishes as the sucrose concentration is increased. It might be recalled that the acid concentration is kept constant in each series. The diminution of the *initial* temperature rise with increase of the sucrose concentration in a series might, therefore, be ascribed to (a) increase in the heat capacity of the solution with the increasing concentration of the solute, (b) diminution in the dilution of heat of the acid due to the presence of sucrose, (c) increase of the heat of dilution of sucrose solution, which is known to be negative (*cf.* Vallender and Perman, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1931, 27, 133) by increasing the concentration of the solution. From considerations indicated already and data presented in Table V, showing that the specific heat of the sucrose solution diminishes by increasing its concentration, it is seen that factor (a) is not the operative factor. From the work of Vallender and Perman (*loc. cit.*), Stackelberg (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1898, 26, 533), Ewan (*ibid.*, 1894, 14, 409), Porter (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1917, 13, 123) and Hunter (*ibid.*, 1926, 22, 194) it would appear that the order of magnitude for the temperature change due to the negative heat of the dilution of even the most concentrated sucrose solutions employed in these experiments is 0.001° , which is negligible compared with the *initial* temperature rise measured (*cf.* curves 1 to 4 in Fig. 6), *viz.*, $0.86-0.09^\circ$. Direct measurements made with sucrose solutions in the concentration

range of 1-6% of sucrose showed that the fall of temperature due to the heat of dilution was but insensible. The factor (c) would appear, therefore, to be insufficient to explain the effect mentioned above. It is considered, therefore, that (b) represents its most probable cause. In this connection it might be pointed out that the temperature rise due to the dilution of 50 c.c. of 4.92, 4.84, and 5 N-HCl solutions by 250 c.c. of water was found to be greater than that observed when any of the sucrose solutions was employed (*cf.* curves 1-4 in Fig. 6; also Table V) instead of water. From a knowledge of the mass of a solution and of the corresponding amount of sucrose, A, the amount of the water present in the solution is known (*cf.* column 3, Table V).

Now general considerations and some actual observations carried out with 5N-HCl solution diluted with volumes of water

in the range, 200-300 c.c. show that the corresponding temperature rise is proportional to the amount of water used in the process of

FIG. 4.

0.41N-HCl.

Curves 1 to 6 refer to 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, and 30 % of sucrose soln. respectively.

FIG. 3.

0.82N-HCl.

Curves 1 to 7 refer to 0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25 and 30% of sucrose soln. respectively. Curve 4 of Fig. 3 obtained from specimen curve 6 of Fig. 6.

dilution. The amount of water thus calculated from the values of the *initial* temperature rise (*cf.* curves 1-4 in Fig. 6) was found to be appreciably less than *A*, in by far the majority of cases. This shows therefore, that a certain amount of water in the solution is not involved in the process of the acid dilution. Presumably therefore, it is bound up in the *hydration* of sucrose in the solution. Results of the detailed investigation carried out to examine this possibility will be communicated shortly.

FIG. 5.

Curve 1 refers to Table I, Fig. 1.

Curves 2-4 refer to Table II-IV and Fig. 2-4 respectively.

Curve 5 shows the variation of sp. heat (scale on the right) with change of sucrose conc. = *m* (scale on the top).

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FIG. 6.

Curves 1-4—Initial rise in temp. due to dilution of HCl by sucrose soln.
 Curve 5—Temp. rise due to a constant current passed in equal vol. of differently concentrated sucrose soln. ; points p, q and r refer to solns. of invert sugar together with the acid used (for other data cf. Table V and also curve 5, Fig. 5).
 Curve 6—Shows the Beckmann temp. before and during inversion (cf. curve no 4 of Fig. 8.). The quantity BC' obtained by extrapolation of DC in curve 6, gives the initial rise of temp. plotted in curves 1-4, mentioned above.

SUMMARY.

1. Results are given for the temperature rise measured adiabatically during the initial stages of the inversion of sucrose solutions containing 2 to 30 g. of the solute in 100 c.c. of the reaction mixture by 0.4 to 0.9N-HCl. An equation is deduced to give k , the velocity coefficient from these time-temperature curves. k tends to increase by increasing the sucrose concentration if that of the acid is kept constant. This result has been shown to be contrary to the requirements of the law of mass action if the rôle of water be assumed to be merely hydrolytic. This change of k with sucrose concentration has been found to depend upon the acid concentration.

2. The specific heats of sucrose solutions have been determined in the range mentioned above. This quantity is found to diminish regularly by increasing the strength of the solution.

3. The heat of dilution of hydrochloric acid solutions has been found to diminish when sucrose solutions are used instead of water, which has been ascribed to the removal of some water from the solvent phase in the hydration of the solute.

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